

EBFMC25-OP-82 · A Case of CMV Mononucleosis Presenting with Prolonged Fever in an Immunocompetent Patient

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Cytomegalovirus (CMV) is a double-stranded DNA virus belonging to the Herpesviridae family. Primary CMV infections in immunocompetent individuals are usually asymptomatic or present with mild clinical symptoms. However, in rare cases, they may manifest with prolonged fever, hepatitis, or mononucleosis-like syndromes. Mononucleosis-like illness typically presents with fever, pharyngitis, lymphadenopathy, fatigue, and lymphocytosis characterized by atypical lymphocytes. The diagnosis of acute CMV infection is based on the detection of specific anti-CMV IgM antibodies by serological methods or the identification of viral DNA via CMV DNA PCR testing. In this report, we aim to highlight the importance of considering acute CMV infection in the differential diagnosis of a case presenting with prolonged fever and hepatitis in an immunocompetent individual.

Case Presentation: A 37-year-old immunocompetent male patient presented with complaints of fever, chills, sweating, fatigue, loss of appetite, and approximately 4 kg weight loss persisting for three weeks. On physical examination, the patient was in good general condition, with no lymphadenopathy, pharyngeal hyperemia, abnormal breath sounds, cardiac murmur, or abdominal tenderness. Hepatosplenomegaly was absent. Initial laboratory findings revealed a white blood cell count (WBC) of $14.16 \times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$, lymphocyte count (LYM) of $9.33 \times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$ (66%), hemoglobin (Hb) of 14.8 g/dL, C-reactive protein (CRP) of 56.93 mg/dL, ALT: 168.7 U/L, AST: 104.7 U/L, and LDH: 451 U/L. Lymphocytic leukocytosis and elevated liver enzymes were noted. Thoracic and abdominal CT scans were unremarkable. Differential diagnoses including Brucella, EBV, HIV, hepatitis viruses, toxoplasmosis, endocarditis, leukemia, and lymphoma were investigated and all results were within normal limits or negative. Peripheral blood smear demonstrated 50% atypical lymphocytes. Anti-CMV

IgM was found to be positive. EBV infection was ruled out based on negative EBV VCA IgM serology and the absence of classical clinical features.

Discussion: The patient was diagnosed with acute CMV infection and was managed with symptomatic supportive care. During follow-up, liver function tests normalized, fever resolved, and his overall condition improved. In cases of prolonged fever accompanied by lymphocytosis, CMV infection should be considered in the differential diagnosis of infectious mononucleosis alongside EBV. In this case, the absence of lymphadenopathy and pharyngitis, along with negative EBV serology, supported the diagnosis of CMV.

Conclusion: It is essential to consider CMV infection in the primary care setting when evaluating patients with unexplained prolonged fever and elevated transaminases.

PEER REVIEW STATEMENT

This paper has undergone a double-blind peer review process and has been approved by the scientific committee of the conference.

KEYWORDS

Cytomegalovirus, CMV, prolonged fever, mononucleosis, immunocompetent, differential diagnosis

INTRODUCTION

Cytomegalovirus (CMV) is a double-stranded DNA virus belonging to the *Herpesviridae* family. It most commonly causes clinical manifestations such as viremia, pneumonia, esophagitis, colitis, and retinitis in immunosuppressed and organ transplant patients. Primary CMV infections in immunocompetent individuals are usually asymptomatic or present with mild clinical symptoms. However, in rare cases, they may manifest with prolonged fever, hepatitis, or mononucleosis-like syndromes. Severe presentations of CMV in otherwise healthy individuals have also been documented (Rafailidis et al., 2008). Mononucleosis-like illness typically presents with fever, pharyngitis, lymphadenopathy, fatigue, and lymphocytosis characterized by atypical lymphocytes. Acute cytomegalovirus hepatitis cases in healthy adults have also been reported (Güler et al., 2013). The diagnosis of acute CMV infection is based on the detection of specific anti-CMV IgM antibodies by serological methods or the identification of viral DNA via CMV DNA PCR testing. In immunocompetent patients, supportive care is usually sufficient, and antiviral therapy is rarely required. A recent review emphasized the clinical spectrum of CMV infections, including their atypical presentations (Kocaman, 2022). In this report, we aim to highlight the importance of considering acute CMV infection in the differential diagnosis of a case presenting with prolonged fever and hepatitis in an immunocompetent individual.

CASE PRESENTATION

A 37-year-old immunocompetent male patient presented with complaints of fever, chills, sweating, fatigue, loss of appetite, and approximately 4 kg weight loss persisting for three weeks. On physical examination, the patient was in good general condition, with no lymphadenopathy, pharyngeal hyperemia, abnormal breath sounds, cardiac murmur, or abdominal tenderness. Hepatosplenomegaly was absent. Initial laboratory findings revealed a white blood cell count (WBC) of $14.16 \times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$, lymphocyte count (LYM) of $9.33 \times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$ (66%), hemoglobin (Hb) of 14.8 g/dL, C-reactive protein (CRP) of 56.93 mg/dL, ALT: 168.7 U/L, AST: 104.7 U/L, and LDH: 451 U/L (Table 1). Lymphocytic leukocytosis and elevated liver enzymes were noted. Thoracic and abdominal CT scans were unremarkable. Differential diagnoses including Brucella, EBV, HIV, hepatitis viruses, toxoplasmosis, endocarditis, leukemia, and lymphoma were investigated, and all results were within normal limits or negative. Peripheral blood smear demonstrated 50% atypical lymphocytes. Anti-CMV IgM was found to be positive. EBV infection was ruled out based on negative EBV VCA IgM serology and the absence of classical clinical features. The patient was diagnosed with acute CMV infection and was managed with symptomatic supportive care. During follow-up, liver function tests normalized, fever resolved, and his overall condition improved.

Table 1

Test	18.02.2025	28.02.2025
WBC (10 ³ /μL)	14.16	19.38
HGB (g/dL)	14.8	14.0
PLT (10 ³ /μL)	382	331.0
AST (U/L)	104.7	50.8
ALT (U/L)	168.7	60.3
CRP (mg/dL)	56.93	37.05
Erythrocyte Sedimentation Rate (mm/h)	–	48.0
Anti-CMV IgM (COI)	2.36 (Positive)	–
EBV VCA IgM	Negative	–
Anti-HCV (COI)	0.194 (Negative)	–
Anti-HIV (COI)	0.189 (Negative)	–
Brucella (Rose Bengal + Tube Agglutination)	Negative	–

DISCUSSION

In cases of prolonged fever accompanied by lymphocytosis, CMV infection should be considered in the differential diagnosis of infectious mononucleosis alongside EBV. While EBV infection typically presents with prominent pharyngitis and lymphadenopathy, these findings are often milder or absent in CMV infection. Distinction between EBV and CMV can be made using specific serological tests such as EBV VCA IgM, and this diagnostic approach is supported by recent clinical reviews (Naughton et al., 2021). In this case, the absence of lymphadenopathy and pharyngitis, along with negative EBV serology, supported the diagnosis of CMV. Additionally, workup for endocarditis and malignancy, including blood cultures, peripheral smear, and imaging studies, were negative. The absence of rash, arthritis, or serositis ruled out autoimmune diseases, and the lack of recurrent neurological symptoms made demyelinating diseases such as multiple sclerosis unlikely. It is important for primary care physicians to be familiar with the clinical spectrum of CMV (Taylor, 2003).

CONCLUSION

It is essential for family physicians and primary care providers to consider CMV infection in the differential diagnosis when encountering patients with unexplained prolonged fever and elevated liver enzymes. Early recognition of CMV in such cases can help prevent unnecessary diagnostic procedures, reduce healthcare costs, and avoid inappropriate treatments such as unnecessary antibiotics or empirical antiviral therapies. In primary care settings, where initial evaluations for more common causes of fever often begin, maintaining clinical suspicion for CMV is crucial—especially when standard workups yield inconclusive results. Enhancing awareness of CMV's clinical presentation in immunocompetent individuals can contribute significantly to timely diagnosis, appropriate management, and improved patient outcomes in general practice.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

There is no commercial, financial, or personal conflict of interest in this study.

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